

Navigating the origins of the Maiden Tower, Mornington, Co. Meath

KILLIAN DOWNING

Introduction

Since the sixteenth century, the Maiden Tower has stood as a prominent landmark overlooking maritime activity along the Boyne estuary. Its commanding presence has long inspired legend, folklore, and reflection.¹ Writing in *The Dublin Penny Journal* in 1833, Robert Armstrong remarked that the tower, ‘standing in isolated solitude, braves the tempest’s fury, and seems to look down with indifference on succeeding fleeting generations of busy mortals’, a description that conveys both its physical presence and its perceived detachment from the changing world around it.² Despite its enduring visibility, the precise date of its construction remains uncertain. Drawing on several archival sources, including a reference to the tower in 1571, this article examines its origins within the context of Elizabethan maritime trade and coastal defence.

Elizabethan Origins

The Maiden Tower is thought to have been constructed during the reign

Figure 1: Maiden tower, near Drogheda, woodcut print, [c.1833]. (Courtesy of the National Library of Ireland)

of Elizabeth I (1558–1603), the “Maiden Queen”.³ Prior to the construction of the river walls, navigational beacons, and lighthouses between the late eighteenth and nineteenth centuries, the Maiden Tower and the adjacent pillar known as the Lady’s Finger served as navigational aids for vessels entering the Boyne estuary.⁴ Approaching ships would align the Lady’s Finger behind the tower, establishing a safe leading line over the sandbar to enter the river channel.⁵ Writing in 1833, Robert Armstrong noted that no historical records survive regarding the construction or purpose of the tower and, like John D’Alton in his *History of Drogheda* (1844), inferred that its location indicated it functioned as a landmark for the safety of shipping using Drogheda Port.⁶ Although primary sources on the development of Drogheda and its port in the sixteenth and early seventeenth centuries are limited, some surviving records provide evidence and historical context.⁷

Drogheda Port

Drawing on Ned McHugh's extensive research, it is clear that Drogheda functioned as an important medieval port, in which shipbuilding and maritime crafts were actively encouraged through royal commands and murage grants from the thirteenth century.⁸ In the early fourteenth century, the construction of a new quay and a stone tower on the northern riverbank signalled the port's economic growth and prosperity.⁹ Trade networks expanded to include Chester, Bristol, Flanders, France, Iceland, Spain, Poland, and Portugal.¹⁰

However, the small harbour area, narrow river channel, tidal sandbar, and siltation presented significant navigational challenges.¹¹ As McHugh notes, 'the simple fact was that geography and nature conspired to check the progress of the port.'¹² These constraints likely contributed to Drogheda being described as a 'bad haven' by the Lord Deputy of Ireland, Sir Anthony St Leger (c.1496–1559), in a report to Henry VIII (1491–1547) in April 1543.¹³ In the same report, Dublin was also labelled as a bad haven, facing comparable navigational difficulties, and in 1545 St Leger described both Dublin and Drogheda as 'evil and dangerous' in correspondence to Lord Chancellor Thomas Wriothesley (1505–1550).¹⁴

The Tower of Drogheda

One of the earliest references to the Maiden Tower appears in the 1582 minutes of the Dublin City Assembly Rolls, documented in the *Calendar of Ancient Records of Dublin*.¹⁵ Since the fifteenth century, the Dublin Assembly had authorised the payment of perch money to the city's water bailiffs, a 'perch' being a navigational marker used to guide ships into port or around hazards such as sandbars.¹⁶ In 1577, Dublin water bailiffs were instructed to establish a perch or buoy on the South Bull (Poolbeg) sandbar using the profits from shipping.¹⁷ By January 1582, a lack of progress prompted the Assembly to issue a new lease with terms to Richard Condran, Water Bailiff, authorising him to erect a perch or buoy using the, '...proffytes formerlie appoynted and layde downe by assemblie uppon all shippes, barques and botes that shall com into the porte or haven of this cittie...'¹⁸

On 22 July 1582, a related minute records the granting of a lease to aldermen Nicholas Duffe (Mayor, 1579–1580) and Nicholas Ball (Mayor, 1582–1583), permitting them to, ‘...builde a towre uppon the Ringesend, of such height and streynth as shalbe of a perpetuall contynuanck lick the towre of Drogheda...’¹⁹ In his *History of Drogheda* (1844), D’Alton linked the proposed construction of this tower to a charter granted by Elizabeth I, which, in his view, established both the era and function of the Maiden Tower.²⁰ He elaborated: ‘A charter of her Majesty, granting certain tolls and customs to the corporation of Dublin, in aid of erecting at Poolbeg a tower, similar to that recently built at the entrance of the harbour of Drogheda, at once establishes the era and use of the latter edifice.’²¹

A later minute of the Dublin City Assembly records that a perch had been constructed but had subsequently collapsed, and by October 1588 Nicholas Ball had surrendered his claim to any profits derived from it.²² Responsibility for the tower’s construction was granted to Captain George Thornton with a deadline of Michaelmas 1589 (29 September). However, no tower was built at the site until the construction of Poolbeg Lighthouse in 1764.²³ The long delay underscores the difficulties of maritime infrastructure projects in Dublin and suggests that the Maiden Tower may originally have been financed through customs and port charges on shipping.

Sir William Fitzwilliam

A 1571 reference to the Maiden Tower appears in the papers of Sir William Fitzwilliam (1526–1599), an English administrator who served Elizabeth I as Vice-Treasurer, Lord Justice, and Lord Deputy of Ireland.²⁴ Fitzwilliam is remembered for his brutal suppression of Irish rebellions, the systematic execution of Spanish Armada shipwreck survivors, and his role as Governor of Fotheringhay Castle in Northamptonshire, where Mary, Queen of Scots, was tried and executed in 1587.

On 7 May 1571, Lord Justice Fitzwilliam, dispatched a Dublin merchant, Henry Dillon, to monitor the movements and activities of Thomas Stukeley (c.1525–1578) an English mercenary suspected of preparing an invasion of Ireland. In April 1571, Stukeley had sailed from Waterford to Viveiro,

Spain, following his loss of power and patronage in Ireland, where he had quarrelled with officials and faced accusations of treason.²⁵

On 20 May 1571, Dillon wrote to Fitzwilliam, explaining that strong easterly winds had prevented his departure from Dublin. He therefore travelled overnight to Drogheda to secure passage on a ship to Spain. Arriving early in the morning, Dillon remarked upon the 'new haven of Drogheda', making specific reference to the Maiden Tower:

...I came afar for full see the new haven of Drogheda where I found a ship of Croesyc [Le Croisic, France] and a ship of St John de Luce [Saint-Jean-de-Luz, France], which had their yards across ready to make sail the same tide, but the wind was at east and continued so ever since, whereby they could not get forth and yet if the wind were good they can scant get now forth of the bar because of the nepe tides but the great ship of St. John de Luce is in the pole towards the Maiden Tower.²⁶

The location of the 'pole' mentioned in Dillon's letter may correspond to the anchorage used by larger three-masted ships depicted downstream from St. Mary's Bridge in Barnabe Googe's map of Drogheda of 1574.²⁷ Googe (also spelt Goche) (1540–1594), was a government official sent to Ireland by William Cecil, 1st Baron Burghley (1520–1598), chief adviser to Elizabeth I. In a letter to Burghley, Googe elaborated: 'I send your Lordshyp the plott of the towne of Tredagh [Drogheda], seated upon two hylles, the haven passynge betwyxt them, the preatyst towne thatt hetherto I have seen in thys contrey.'²⁸

Dillon's letter referring to the Maiden Tower complicates D'Alton's interpretation that the tower was 'recently built' in connection with the proposed Poolbeg tower of 1582, indicating instead that it existed by, and likely before, 1571.²⁹ Consequently, the origins of the Maiden Tower's construction may lie in the 1560s.

Fortifications and Repairs

On 28 November 1567, a brief of suits was submitted to Queen Elizabeth by the Mayor, Sheriffs, Burgesses, and Commons of Drogheda, requesting a ten-year exemption from customs duties to fund repairs to the town's haven, bridge, quay, walls, and south gate, after which the customs would continue under a fixed rent.³⁰ The petition was endorsed by the joint Lord Justices, William Fitzwilliam and Robert Weston (c.1522–1573), the Bishop of Meath, Hugh Brady (c.1527–1584), and the members of the Irish Privy Council. Drogheda's strategic importance was emphasised to Elizabeth, with the Lord Justices noting: 'This town, fronting the northern borders of this realm, is a necessary strength and key for Her Majesty's subjects there and helps the rest of the Pale.'³¹

Drogheda was not alone in seeking repairs and fortification during this period. In 1568, the joint commanders of Carrickfergus Castle, Sir William Piers and Sir Nicholas Malby, warned the Lord Justices of the threat posed by Turlough Luineach O'Neill's (c.1530–1595) forces lying at the Skerries off Portrush, noting, '...this shows O'Neill's devices and how necessary it is to hold and inhabit the coast... the coast should be held to prevent their landing.' The English administration is argued to have preferred the development of Carrickfergus' port over Drogheda, as it was considered safer to strengthen a port outside the Pale for security.³² In 1569, Elizabeth granted Carrickfergus a charter of incorporation, conferring privileges and jurisdiction similar to those of Drogheda, including repairs to the port and the fortification of the town walls by the Crown.³³

Despite support from the Irish Privy Council and the Bishop of Meath, Drogheda's 1567 petition was unsuccessful.³⁴ However, Fionnán Tuite has suggested that the town financed the development of its port and walls, aligning economic and infrastructural priorities, and notes, 'The late 1560s was an important turning point in the growth and expansion of Drogheda's port, and its merchant community.'³⁵

While Drogheda's linen and wool industries declined toward the late sixteenth century due to changes in Crown licensing and trade policy, Nicholas Bathe can be identified as a prominent and prosperous member

Figure 2: The Bathe House, St. Laurence Street, Drogheda, sepia wash drawing on paper by Robert Armstrong, 1823. (Courtesy of the Highlanes Gallery, Drogheda)

of Drogheda's mercantile community.³⁶ In 1570, he commissioned the construction of Bathe House (Figure 2), demonstrating that some merchants possessed the resources to fund substantial building projects. Bathe later served as Mayor of Drogheda in 1577, and was empowered by Elizabeth I to investigate unpaid customs rents, suggesting that merchants may have had the capacity to cooperate on infrastructure projects, such as the Maiden Tower, to safeguard shipping and protect trade.³⁷

Legend and Folklore

The Maiden Tower has long been a source of legend and folklore, some of which was recorded in the Irish Folklore Commission's Schools' Collection

(Bailiúchán na Scol) between 1937 and 1939.³⁸ The mythology surrounding the tower reflects themes found in classical narratives such as those of Aegeus and Theseus, and Hero and Leander, stories that centre on the tragic misinterpretation of signals and the ensuing death by grief. Writing in *The Beauties of the Boyne* (1849) William Wilde recounts:

Tradition says it was erected by a fair lady, to watch the return of her betrothed from a far-distant country, whither he was obliged to journey upon the eve of their nuptials. It was agreed beforehand that, if the lover returned successful, he should hoist a milk-white banner; but if the contrary, a red flag should float from his mast-head. The preconcerted signal was forgotten, and the knight, seeing the tower, which his true love had erected during his absence to watch his return, and mistaking it for the watch-tower of an enemy and an invader, instantly displayed the blood-red flag, whereon the disconsolate maiden precipitated herself from the top of the tower, and was dashed to atoms.³⁹

Architecture and Ownership

D'Alton (1844) records that the Maiden Tower was built on oak piles, with a spiral staircase leading to a barrel-vaulted ceiling and a trapdoor onto a battlemented parapet overlooking the Boyne estuary.⁴⁰ Its elevated position and defensive features suggest it may have functioned as a lookout post or watchtower.⁴¹ William Wilde (1849) notes the parapet was '...reached by a small aperture, which could easily be covered with a large stone, so that it might, in case of siege, be rendered inaccessible from within.'⁴² The earliest recorded drawing of the Maiden Tower, dated 1783 (Figure 3), depicts its defensive arrow loops and battlemented parapet, the latter of which may have been rebuilt or repaired in the nineteenth century.⁴³ Three interconnecting mortises on each side at the top of the tower suggest a lookout platform may once have existed.

In 1559, lands and leases around Mornington, the site of the Maiden Tower, were transferred from the late Sir William Brabazon (d.1552),

Figure 3: Views of Maiden Tower near Drogheda, drawing on paper by Austin Cooper and Samuel Walker, 1783. (Courtesy of the National Library of Ireland).

former Lord Justice of Ireland and Vice-Treasurer of Ireland, to Henry Draycott (c.1510–1572). Draycott was a member of the Irish Privy Council and held several senior English administrative offices, including Chief Remembrancer of the Irish Exchequer, Baron of the Court of Exchequer, and Master of the Rolls in Ireland. He supported the 1567 brief of suits submitted to Queen Elizabeth, and may have had a vested interest in repairs to Drogheda’s port, as his lands were concentrated in East Meath and along the Boyne. Against the background of documented customs evasion, with ships offloading goods at Mornington to avoid customs at Drogheda Port, Draycott likely supported building a watchtower on his land to monitor shipping and deter customs evasion.⁴⁴

Navigational Landmark

Although no known records document the original purpose of the Maiden Tower, there is consensus that it functioned as a landmark for the safety of shipping.⁴⁵ Its strategic position overlooking the Boyne estuary, together with evidence that the tower and the adjacent pillar known as the Lady’s

Finger were roughcast with lime to give a bright appearance, supports their interpretation as navigational landmarks.⁴⁶ It remains uncertain whether the Lady's Finger was constructed with the tower or afterwards. Contemporary to the 1567 petition for the financing of repairs to Drogheda's port, was the Sea Marks Act, 1566, which recognised the importance of maritime commerce and that the safety of shipping depended on reliable coastal landmarks and aids for navigation.⁴⁷

In 1609, the Maiden Tower was mentioned in a charter issued during the reign of James I (1603–1625), granting the Corporation of Drogheda all wrecks of the sea within the port, the water of the Boyne and the fisheries, '...to the deep sea beyond the tower called Maiden Tower.'⁴⁸ McHugh's analysis of shipping casualties in the Drogheda area between 1769 and 1825 underscore why a prominent, bright landmark was essential for the safety of shipping.⁴⁹ Niall Brady and Edward Pollard further observe that the majority of wrecks within the Boyne estuary occurred on the sandbar at the river entrance and on the North and South Bull sandflats.⁵⁰

Defending Drogheda

The threat of invasion was a persistent concern for Drogheda, evidenced as early as the ninth century in the *Annals of the Four Masters*, which record a fleet of sixty Norse ships on the Boyne.⁵¹ In 1409, the threat of invasion resulted in a warship being commissioned at Drogheda to defend the Irish coast from Scottish attack.⁵² Scottish, Spanish and Breton pirates were notoriously active in the Irish Sea, capturing vessels and holding merchants for ransom.⁵³

In May 1545, during Henry VIII's war with France, fears of an invasion extended to Ireland. Lord Deputy, Anthony St Leger, warned the English Privy Council that 'owing to the bruit that the French king would send men to land here with young Gerald [FitzGerald], beacons are erected on the coasts and all the people of the English Pale mustered and ready to resist any such attempt.'⁵⁴ A month later, two fleets amounting to approximately 130 French and Scottish ships were reported off the coast of Drogheda.⁵⁵

Beacon fires, used since Viking times, provided a rapid communication system, transmitting alerts from hill to hill and tower to tower.⁵⁶ For a coastal

town like Drogheda, such early warning systems may have been vital. While the use of coastal beacons in Ireland is documented as early as the thirteenth century at Hook Head, County Wexford, where fires were maintained for the safety of shipping, it remains uncertain, though possible, the Maiden Tower was equipped with a brazier to serve as a warning beacon.⁵⁷

By the late sixteenth century, the English administration's concerns about invasion had shifted to the threat posed by Spain, while the O'Neills of Tyrone continued to challenge English rule from Ulster. In 1571, legislation was proposed to grant Elizabeth I title to all havens in Ireland, both to strengthen coastal defences and to facilitate customs collection, the proposal also included the construction of a castle at Drogheda for defensive purposes.⁵⁸ That same year, Henry Dillon reported to Lord Justice Fitzwilliam that a fleet was assembling at Viveiro under John "Don Juan" of Austria (1547–1578).⁵⁹ Suspecting an invasion involving Philip II, Pope Pius V, and Thomas Stukeley, Fitzwilliam warned Elizabeth of the potential threat, later writing to Lord Burghley, 'If Spain possesses Ireland with 6,000 soldiers, I fear England may look after it as Calais.'⁶⁰ These threats highlight Drogheda's strategic position and the potential role of the Maiden Tower in coastal defence.

Conclusion

This article has drawn on both primary and secondary sources to examine the origins of the Maiden Tower within the context of Elizabethan maritime trade and coastal defence. A 1571 archival reference confirms the tower's existence, establishing it as at least 455 years old and likely constructed during the reign of Elizabeth I. While the Maiden Tower most likely served primarily as a navigational landmark, it may also have functioned as a watchtower for maritime trade or as a defensive structure providing early warning of invasion. It is possible that the tower fulfilled all three roles, reflecting the interconnected nature of commerce, navigation, and security along the Boyne estuary. Further archaeological investigation and archival research could help clarify its precise function, construction, and relationship to the Lady's Finger.

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